

An algebraic approach to the identification of linear continuous systems using Laguerre networks

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Abstract—This paper presents an algebraic approach to linear continuous system identification using Laguerre networks. The proposed approach provides an indirect calculation of the coefficients for the Laguerre expansion of the system's transfer function, based on the Laguerre representations of the system's input and output. The algorithm's computational complexity can be significantly reduced for two specific choices of the input excitation function. The algorithm convergence properties and computational complexity is compared with the classical gradient algorithms. Furthermore, an optimal LQR controller with a state observer is designed using the Laguerre representation of the unknown linear system. Simulation results on a coupled-mass system with unknown parameters and unknown system order demonstrate the effectiveness of the proposed system identification and control methods.

Index Terms—linear system identification, continuous systems, Laguerre networks, batch gradient algorithm, algebraic method

I. INTRODUCTION

The development of mathematical models of systems from observed data is a crucial aspect of control theory. The goal of control-relevant system identification is to obtain an approximate model that can be used to design high-performance controllers. The use of Laguerre functions for system identification has been a promising approach in recent decades [1]. It has proven to be an effective tool in modeling dynamic systems because it can represent asymptotically stable linear systems and provide a computationally simple representation of square integrable signals. Since the Laplace transform of Laguerre functions are rational functions of the complex variable, it is feasible to construct a finite-dimensional approximation of an unknown, possibly infinite-dimensional system using a truncated version of the convergent expansion.

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Laguerre functions have been used to identify various types of dynamic systems. The continuous-time system identification using Laguerre functions is presented in [2] and [3]. In [4] discrete-time systems identification using Laguerre network is discussed. Additional examples can be found in [5], [6] and [7]. Some examples of using Laguerre networks for the identification of time-delayed systems can be found in [8], [9] and [10]. In [11] and [12] Laguerre functions are applied to nonlinear system identification.

The application of Laguerre functions in control theory is also a very active area of research. The PID controller tuning based on the Laguerre series is considered in [13], [14]. The adaptive controllers based on the Laguerre system representation are proposed in [15] and [16]. Recent papers mostly use Laguerre networks in the context of model predictive control for approximation of the control variable [17], [18], [19]. Adaptive pole selection of the Laguerre network in model predictive control is considered in [20].

While there have been significant theoretical advancements in off-line identification methods, limited research has been done on using Laguerre functions for online identification, [21]. In this paper, a novel algebraic approach to online system identification using Laguerre functions is proposed. The proposed algorithm differs from conventional methods based on the least squares method or gradient algorithms. Instead of direct calculation of the Laguerre coefficients of the transfer function, it employs indirect calculation using the Laguerre coefficients of the input and output signals. The algorithm is based on the algebraic properties of transfer functions product [22], [23], which enable computationally efficient calculation of the transfer function coefficients.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. In Section II, the Laguerre networks in the context of system identification are presented. The algorithm for transfer function identification and related controller-observer system are presented in Section III. The simulation results on a multi-DOF system are presented in Section IV. Finally, the concluding remarks are

summarized in Section V.

II. LAGUERRE NETWORK

A. Orthonormal functions

Real functions $L_i(t)$ form a set of orthonormal functions on interval $[0, \infty)$ if the following property is satisfied

$$\int_0^{\infty} L_i(t)L_j(t)dt = \delta_{ij}, \quad (1)$$

for $i, j = 1, 2, \dots$, where δ_{ij} is Kronecker delta symbol.

Any square integrable function $f(t)$ that satisfies

$$\int_0^{\infty} f^2(t)dt < \infty, \quad (2)$$

can be represented as the infinite sum of orthonormal functions

$$f(t) = \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} c_i L_i(t), \quad (3)$$

where $c_i, i = 1, 2, \dots$ are coefficients defined as

$$c_i = \int_0^{\infty} L_i(t)f(t)dt. \quad (4)$$

By taking the first N terms in (3), the infinite sum representation of the function $f(t)$ can be approximated by the truncated expansion

$$\hat{f}(t) = \sum_{i=1}^N c_i L_i(t). \quad (5)$$

The function $f(t)$ can be arbitrarily closely approximated by (5) by increasing number of terms N .

B. Laguerre functions

The orthonormal Laguerre functions are defined as

$$L_i(t) = \frac{\sqrt{2p}}{(i-1)!} e^{pt} \frac{d^{i-1}}{dt^{i-1}} (t^{i-1} e^{-2pt}), \quad (6)$$

for $i = 1, 2, \dots$, where $p > 0$ is a time scaling factor. The Laplace transform of the Laguerre functions are rational functions, given in complex domain as

$$L_i(s) = \int_0^{\infty} L_i(t)e^{-st}dt = \frac{\sqrt{2p}}{s+p} \left(\frac{s-p}{s+p} \right)^{i-1}. \quad (7)$$

By transforming the given equations in state space form as

$$\dot{\mathbf{L}}(t) = \mathbf{A}_p \mathbf{L}(t), \quad (8)$$

where $\mathbf{L}(t) = [L_1(t) \ L_2(t) \ \dots \ L_N(t)]^T$ with initial conditions $\mathbf{L}(0) = \sqrt{2p}[1 \ 1 \ \dots \ 1]^T$, and

$$\mathbf{A}_p = \begin{bmatrix} -p & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ -2p & -p & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \ddots & \ddots & \vdots \\ -2p & \dots & -2p & -p \end{bmatrix}, \quad (9)$$

the function (5) can be rewritten as

$$f(t) = \mathbf{c}^T \mathbf{L}(t), \quad (10)$$

where $\mathbf{c} = [c_1 \ c_2 \ \dots \ c_N]^T$ is a vector of unknown coefficients.

C. Transfer function identification

The impulse response function $g(t)$ of a asymptotically stable continuous linear system is a square integrable function which satisfies property (2), so that the transfer function $G(s) = \mathcal{L}\{g(s)\}$ can be represented as the Laguerre expansion

$$G(s) = \sum_{i=1}^N c_i L_i(s). \quad (11)$$

Input-output representation of a linear SISO system can be written in complex domain as

$$y(s) = G(s)u(s) = \sum_{i=1}^N c_i L_i(s)u(s) = \sum_{i=1}^N c_i z_i(s), \quad (12)$$

where $z_i(s) = L_i(s)u(s)$, for $i = 1, 2, \dots, N$, are state variables in complex domain, and the state space representation in the time domain is

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\mathbf{z}} &= \mathbf{A}_p \mathbf{z} + \mathbf{b}_p u, \\ y &= \mathbf{c}^T \mathbf{z}, \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

where $\mathbf{z} = [z_1 \ z_2 \ \dots \ z_N]$, $\mathbf{c} = [c_1 \ c_2 \ \dots \ c_N]$, the matrix \mathbf{A}_p is defined by (9) and $\mathbf{b}_p = \mathbf{L}(0)$.

The system (13) is non-autonomous version of the orthonormal system (8), but the responses $z_i(t) = \mathcal{L}^{-1}\{L_i(s)u(s)\}$ are not orthogonal functions, and expression (4) can not be used for the calculation of unknown coefficients \mathbf{c} . Usually, in that case, the least square method is used for off-line identification of the unknown coefficients, which has drawbacks regarding the ill-conditioning problem related to the Gram matrix inversion. Iterative methods like gradient algorithms provide an online estimation of parameters and a well-conditioned solution.

D. Gradient algorithm for coefficients estimation

For the online identification of coefficients c_i where $i = 1, 2, \dots, N$, iterative optimization method can be used, such as a gradient algorithm

$$\frac{d\mathbf{c}}{dt} = -\mu \frac{\partial J(\mathbf{c})}{\partial \mathbf{c}}, \quad (14)$$

where μ is the learning coefficient of the gradient algorithm and $J(\mathbf{c})$ is objective function. If the objective function is expressed as the error of the truncated representation of the system output

$$J(\mathbf{c}) = \frac{1}{2} [y(t) - \mathbf{c}(t)^T \mathbf{z}(t)]^2, \quad (15)$$

gradient algorithm is

$$\dot{\mathbf{c}}(t) = \mu [y(t) - \mathbf{c}(t)^T \mathbf{z}(t)] \mathbf{z}(t), \quad \mathbf{c}(0) = \mathbf{c}_0, \quad (16)$$

where \mathbf{c}_0 is the vector of initial conditions.

With assumption that objective function is obtain by integrating square of the error on interval $[0, t]$,

$$J(\mathbf{c}) = \frac{1}{2} \int_0^t [y(\tau) - \mathbf{c}(\tau)^T \mathbf{z}(\tau)]^2 d\tau, \quad (17)$$

so called batch gradient algorithm is obtained as:

$$\begin{aligned}\dot{\mathbf{c}}(t) &= -\mu [\mathbf{M}(t)\mathbf{c}(t) - \mathbf{w}(t)], & \mathbf{c}(0) &= \mathbf{c}_0, \\ \dot{\mathbf{M}}(t) &= \mathbf{z}(t)\mathbf{z}(t)^T, & \mathbf{M}(0) &= \mathbf{0}_{N \times N}, \\ \dot{\mathbf{w}}(t) &= \mathbf{z}(t)y(t), & \mathbf{w}(0) &= \mathbf{0}_{N \times 1}.\end{aligned}\quad (18)$$

The standard gradient algorithm is computationally less expensive than the batch gradient algorithm, but the parameter estimation error is too large for efficient applications in control systems design.

III. ALGEBRAIC APPROACH TO TRANSFER FUNCTION IDENTIFICATION

The unknown linear SISO system is represented by the following set of linear differential equations

$$\begin{aligned}\dot{\mathbf{x}} &= \mathbf{A}_s \mathbf{x} + \mathbf{b}_s u, \\ y &= \mathbf{c}_s^T \mathbf{x},\end{aligned}\quad (19)$$

where $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^n$ is the state vector, u is the input function, y is the system output, and \mathbf{A}_s , \mathbf{b}_s and \mathbf{c}_s are constant matrices of the system's state-space representation. The matrix elements and system dimension n are completely unknown. The only assumption is that the unknown system is asymptotically stable, and that only output $y(t)$ is measurable.

The identification goal is to approximate the system transfer function $G_s(s) = \mathbf{c}_s^T (s\mathbf{I}_{n \times n} - \mathbf{A}_s)^{-1} \mathbf{b}_s$ by the Laguerre expansion (11), based on the known input function $u(t)$ and measurable output $y(t)$.

The input and output function can be represented by the Laguerre expansions

$$u(s) = \sum_{i=1}^N b_i L_i(s), \quad y(s) = \sum_{i=1}^N a_i L_i(s), \quad (20)$$

where the coefficients a_i and b_i can be directly calculated by expression (4). The coefficients c_i of Laguerre representation of the transfer function can be calculated indirectly, as will be shown in the rest of this section.

By multiplying Laguerre series of the transfer function $G(s)$ and input function $u(s)$, and using the multiplication property of Laguerre functions

$$L_i(s)L_j(s) = L_1(s)L_{i+j-1}(s), \quad (21)$$

the next expression is obtained

$$\begin{aligned}y(s) &= G(s)u(s) = \sum_{j=1}^N \sum_{i=1}^N c_j b_i L_j(s)L_i(s) \\ &= L_1(s) \sum_{j=1}^N \sum_{i=1}^N c_j b_i L_{i+j-1}(s).\end{aligned}\quad (22)$$

By introducing the change of indexes $k = i + j - 1$, the expression (22) can be rewritten as

$$y(s) = L_1(s) \sum_{j=1}^N \sum_{k=j}^N c_j b_{k-j+1} L_k(s). \quad (23)$$

where the higher-order Laguerre functions $L_k(s)$, for $k > N$, are neglected.

Using the rule for interchange the order of summation

$$\sum_{j=1}^N \sum_{k=j}^N A_{jk} = \sum_{k=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^k A_{jk}, \quad (24)$$

Eq. (23) can be rewritten as

$$\begin{aligned}y(s) &= L_1(s) \sum_{k=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^k c_j b_{k-j+1} L_k(s) \\ &= L_1(s) \sum_{k=1}^N r_k L_k(s),\end{aligned}\quad (25)$$

where

$$r_k = \sum_{j=1}^k c_j b_{k-j+1}. \quad (26)$$

After the application of another multiplication property of Laguerre functions [24],

$$L_i(s)L_j(s) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2p}} (L_{i+j-1}(s) - L_{i+j}(s)), \quad (27)$$

and separation of the sum, the expression (25) becomes

$$y(s) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2p}} \sum_{k=1}^N r_k L_k(s) - \frac{1}{\sqrt{2p}} \sum_{k=1}^N r_k L_{k+1}(s). \quad (28)$$

Applying the another change of the indexes, where $j = k + 1$ is introduced, expression for the output signal $y(t)$ from (20) can be presented as

$$y(s) = \frac{r_1}{\sqrt{2p}} L_1(s) + \frac{1}{\sqrt{2p}} \sum_{k=2}^N (r_k - r_{k-1}) L_k(s), \quad (29)$$

where the higher-order term $L_{N+1}(s)$ is neglected. By comparing expression (29) with (20), it follows

$$a_1 = \frac{r_1}{\sqrt{2p}}, \quad a_k = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2p}} (r_k - r_{k-1}), \quad (30)$$

for $k = 2, 3, \dots, N$. The expressions (30) and (26) provide direct algebraic relations between coefficients of Laguerre expansion for the system input, output and transfer function.

The previous expressions can be presented in more transparent way by introducing the following matrices

$$\mathbf{W} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ -1 & 1 & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 1 & \cdots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & \cdots & 0 & -1 & 1 \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{R} = \begin{bmatrix} b_1 & 0 & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ b_2 & b_1 & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ b_3 & b_2 & b_1 & \cdots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ b_N & \cdots & b_3 & b_2 & b_1 \end{bmatrix},$$

with the vectors of Laguerre coefficients $\mathbf{r} = [r_1 \ r_2 \ \cdots \ r_N]^T$, $\mathbf{a} = [a_1 \ a_2 \ \cdots \ a_N]^T$, $\mathbf{b} = [b_1 \ b_2 \ \cdots \ b_N]^T$ and $\mathbf{c} = [c_1 \ c_2 \ \cdots \ c_N]^T$.

Now, the expressions (30) and (26) can be rewritten in matrix form

$$\mathbf{r} = \mathbf{R}\mathbf{c}, \quad \mathbf{a} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2p}} \mathbf{W}\mathbf{r}, \quad (31)$$

so that final expression for the coefficients of Laguerre expansion of the system transfer function is

$$\mathbf{c} = \sqrt{2p}\mathbf{R}^{-1}\mathbf{W}^{-1}\mathbf{a}. \quad (32)$$

A. Selection of the input excitation function

The matrix \mathbf{R} used in (32) is a lower triangular Toeplitz matrix containing only coefficients b_j of the Laguerre expansion of the input function. That means that the calculation of the coefficient \mathbf{c} can be simplified by choosing a specific input function $u(t)$.

If the vector \mathbf{b} is chosen as $\mathbf{b} = \sqrt{2p}A[1 \ 0 \ \dots \ 0]^T$, where A is a constant parameter that provides tuning of the input signal amplitude, then $\mathbf{R}^{-1} = (\sqrt{2p}A)^{-1}\mathbf{I}_{N \times N}$, so that Eq. (32) becomes $\mathbf{c} = A^{-1}\mathbf{W}^{-1}\mathbf{a}$. The general expression for the inverse of the matrix \mathbf{W} is

$$\mathbf{W}^{-1} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 1 & 1 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & \dots & 1 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (33)$$

so that the final simplified expression is obtained

$$c_k = \frac{1}{A} \sum_{j=1}^k a_j. \quad (34)$$

In that case, input function is

$$u(t) = \sqrt{2p}AL_1(t). \quad (35)$$

The second case which simplifies algorithm complexity is the choice $\mathbf{b} = \sqrt{2p}A[1 \ 1 \ \dots \ 1]^T$. In that case, $\mathbf{R} = \sqrt{2p}A\mathbf{W}^{-1}$, so that Eq. (32) becomes $\mathbf{c} = A^{-1}\mathbf{a}$. In other words, the output of the system is equal to the impulse response function multiplied by a scalar factor A^{-1} , or $y(t) = A^{-1}g(t)$, where $g(t) = \mathcal{L}^{-1}\{G(s)\}$. In that case, input function is

$$u(t) = \sqrt{2p}A \sum_{j=1}^N L_j(t). \quad (36)$$

For the both choices of the input excitation functions $u(t)$, only coefficients \mathbf{a} should be identified online using the filter

$$\dot{\hat{\mathbf{a}}}(t) = y(t)\mathbf{L}(t), \quad \hat{\mathbf{a}}(0) = \mathbf{0}_{N \times 1} \quad (37)$$

where $\hat{\mathbf{a}}(t)$ is the estimation of the vector \mathbf{a} , which can be reached in the case $\mathbf{a} = \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \hat{\mathbf{a}}(t)$. If identification time T is chosen as the time after which the slowest Laguerre function $L_N(t)$ is approximately at zero, then coefficient vector can be approximated as $\mathbf{a} = \hat{\mathbf{a}}(T)$.

B. The output feedback controller design

The Laguerre representation (13) of the unknown linear system (19) can be used for the output feedback controller design. The matrices \mathbf{A}_p , \mathbf{b}_p and identified vector \mathbf{c} of the Laguerre state-space representation (13) will be employed for

the design of the LQR state controller and Luenberger state observer.

The observer inputs are known control variable $u(t)$ and measurable output $y(t)$ of the system (19),

$$\dot{\hat{\mathbf{z}}} = \mathbf{A}_p\hat{\mathbf{z}} + \mathbf{b}_p u + \mathbf{L}(y - \mathbf{c}^T\hat{\mathbf{z}}), \quad (38)$$

where \mathbf{L} is observer gain matrix determined by pole placement method, while the input of the LQR controller is estimated state of the observer $\hat{\mathbf{z}}$,

$$u = -\mathbf{k}^T\hat{\mathbf{z}} + Ry_d, \quad (39)$$

where y_d is the desired constant reference value of the system output. The LQR controller gain \mathbf{k} is determined based on the minimization of objective function

$$J = \int_0^\infty (\mathbf{z}^T\mathbf{Q}\mathbf{z} + ru^2) dt, \quad (40)$$

where \mathbf{Q} and r are positive definite state and input weighted matrices. The feedforward gain R is calculated as

$$R = -\frac{1}{\mathbf{c}^T(\mathbf{A}_p - \mathbf{b}_p\mathbf{k}^T)^{-1}\mathbf{b}_p}. \quad (41)$$

IV. SIMULATION RESULTS

As an example of identification for control, the system of the n_0 coupled masses is considered. The assumption is that all masses, elasticity and dumping coefficients are the same for each degree of the freedom. Dynamical equations of the proposed system are

$$\begin{aligned} m\ddot{y}_1 + d(2\dot{y}_1 - \dot{y}_2) + k(2y_1 - y_2) &= 0, \\ m\ddot{y}_i + d(2\dot{y}_i - \dot{y}_{i-1} - \dot{y}_{i+1}) + k(2y_i - y_{i-1} - y_{i+1}) &= 0, \\ m\ddot{y}_{n_0} + d(2\dot{y}_{n_0} - \dot{y}_{n_0-1}) + k(2y_{n_0} - y_{n_0-1}) &= 0, \end{aligned}$$

where $i = 2, \dots, n_0 - 1$, y_i is the position of the i mass, m is the mass, d is the dumping coefficient and k is the elasticity coefficient. The only measurable system variable is $y = y_1$, while the only actuated degree of freedom is related with the n_0 -th mass. The matrix representation of the system is

$$m\ddot{\mathbf{y}} + \mathbf{D}\dot{\mathbf{y}} + \mathbf{K}\mathbf{y} = \mathbf{b}u, \quad (42)$$

where $\mathbf{D} = d\mathbf{J}$, $\mathbf{K} = k\mathbf{J}$,

$$\mathbf{J} = \begin{bmatrix} 2 & -1 & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ -1 & 2 & -1 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 2 & -1 & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 & -1 & 2 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (43)$$

and $\mathbf{y} = [y_1 \ y_2 \ \dots \ y_{n_0}]^T$, $\mathbf{b} = [0 \ 0 \ \dots \ 1]^T$. By introducing the state variables as $\mathbf{x} = [\mathbf{y}^T \ \dot{\mathbf{y}}^T]^T$, the system can be rewritten in state space form (19), where $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^{2n_0}$, and

$$\mathbf{A}_s = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0}_{n_0 \times n_0} & \mathbf{I}_{n_0 \times n_0} \\ -m^{-1}\mathbf{K} & -m^{-1}\mathbf{D} \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{b}_s = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0}_{n_0 \times 1} \\ m^{-1}\mathbf{b} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (44)$$

and $\mathbf{c}_s = [1 \ 0 \ \dots \ 0]^T \in \mathbb{R}^{2n_0}$.

For simulation purposes, each element has a mass $m = 1$ kg, dumping coefficient $d = 2$ kg/s and elasticity coefficient

Fig. 1. The Laguerre coefficients \mathbf{a} of the system output ($n = 12$, $N = 9$).

$k = 1$ N/m. For the Laguerre filter representation of the system, the time scaling factor is chosen as $p = 0.6$. The learning coefficient of the gradient algorithm is set at $\mu = 50$. Controller's state-cost weighted matrix \mathbf{Q} is diagonal matrix with main diagonal elements set at 0.05, the control weighted factor is $r = 1$, and observer pole is chosen as $\lambda = -0.5$.

The first part of the simulation is done on the coupled masses system with $n_o = 6$ elements, which means that identification is done on the system of $n = 2n_o = 12$ order. The Laguerre filter order in this case is set at $N = 9$.

Fig. 1 shows an estimation of the Laguerre coefficients \mathbf{a} of the output function $y(t) = \mathbf{a}^T \mathbf{L}(t)$ in the case when the input function is chosen as $u(t) = L_1(t)$. It can be observed that all algorithms have a similar rate of convergence toward the stationary value of the parameters, however, the standard gradient algorithm has a large estimation error. On the other hand, both the algebraic approach and the batch gradient algorithm converge toward the same stationary value of the coefficients. These results show that the gradient algorithms do not have any advantage in comparison with the estimation algorithm (37) which is based on expression (4).

The Laguerre coefficients \mathbf{c} of the transfer function can be obtained from the output $y(t) = \mathbf{a}^T \mathbf{z}(t)$ of the system state-space realization (13). In this case, the components of the state vector $\mathbf{z}(t)$ are not orthogonal functions, so estimator (37) can not be directly applied. Nevertheless, gradient algorithms are applicable in the same form as in the previous case. In the case when the input excitation function is chosen as $u(t) = L_1(t)$, the proposed algebraic algorithm provides a simple expression (34) which connects Laguerre coefficients of the transfer function with the coefficients of the output function, estimated by (37). Fig. 2 shows a comparison of the algebraic and gradient algorithms in the case of the estimation of the Laguerre coefficients \mathbf{c} . The compared estimators exhibit similar performances as in the case shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 3 shows the outputs comparison of the unknown system

Fig. 2. The Laguerre coefficients \mathbf{c} of the transfer function ($n = 12$, $N = 9$).

and the Laguerre network with estimated coefficients \mathbf{c} , in the case of input excitation function $u(t) = L_1(t)$.

The main difference between batch gradient algorithm and algebraic approach is in calculation complexity. The dimension of the estimator based on batch gradient algorithm is $3N + N^2$, while the standard gradient and algebraic estimators have dimension $2N$. In other words, for the same level of accuracy, the algebraic approach is much more computationally efficient than the batch gradient algorithm.

Fig. 4 shows the system responses when the LQR controller with state observer is applied, depending on the number of degrees of freedom. The order of the Laguerre estimator is fixed at $N = 12$ for each coupled masses system that needs to be identified, from $n_o = 1$ to $n_o = 9$. The control variable acts on the n_o -th mass and the control objective is the stabilization of the measured position of the first mass around desired position $y_d = 0.1$ m. Also, a constant disturbance with amplitude $d = 0.1$ N is present between 20 and 25 s.

A comparison is made between classical LQR state controller (state LQR) where all states are measurable and the dynamical model of the system is known, and LQR controller with state observer (output LQR) described in the previous section. The system responses of both controllers are similar, while the reaction to the disturbance is almost identical. It should be emphasized that in the case of the output LQR, the system is completely unknown and only the position of the first mass is measurable.

The simulation results show that accurate regulation of the unknown systems can be obtained for different system orders up to $n \approx 2N$. In the case of higher-order systems, a stationary regulation error occurs, which can be removed by including an integral component in the controller or by increasing the dimension of observer [25].

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, an algebraic approach to the identification of the linear continuous system based on Laguerre representation

Fig. 3. The system and Laguerre network input-output signals in the case of identification ($n = 12$, $N = 9$).

Fig. 4. The closed-loop responses of the systems with LQR controller and state observer depending on the number of degrees of freedom.

has been proposed. The proposed method is compared to both standard and batch gradient algorithms. While the standard gradient algorithm does not guarantee accurate system identification, both the batch gradient algorithm and the algebraic estimator provide accurate results. However, the algebraic approach is significantly more computationally efficient than the batch gradient algorithm. In the case of application of the LQR controller with state observer, it is possible to achieve precise regulation of the completely unknown systems of up to twice the size of the Laguerre filter order. The future work will be oriented toward experimental evaluations of the proposed identification method.

REFERENCES

- [1] L. Wang and W. R. Cluett, *From Plant Data to Process Control - Ideas for process identification and PID design*. Taylor & Francis Group, 2000.
- [2] C. T. Chou, M. Verhaegen, and R. Johansson, "Continuous-time Identification of SISO Systems Using Laguerre Functions," *IEEE Transaction on Signal Processing*, vol. 47, no. 2, pp. 349–362, 1999.
- [3] M. Yu, G. Guo, and J. Liu, "Continuous-time Laguerre-based subspace identification utilising nuclear norm minimisation," *International Journal of Systems Science*, vol. 52, no. 1, pp. 157–172, 2021.
- [4] B. Wahlberg, "System identification using Laguerre models," *IEEE Transactions on Automatic Control*, vol. 36, no. 5, pp. 551–562, 1991.
- [5] M. Manngård and H. T. Toivonen, "Identification of low-order models using Laguerre basis function expansions," in *18th IFAC Symposium on System Identification (SYSID 2018)*, vol. 51, no. 15, Stockholm, Sweden, 2018, pp. 72–77.

- [6] M. Coronel, R. Carvajal, and J. C. Aguero, "Identification of Continuous-Time Deterministic System utilizing Orthonormal Basis Functions and Sample Data," in *2019 IEEE CHILEAN Conference on Electrical, Electronics Engineering, Information and Communication Technologies (CHILECON)*, 2019.
- [7] Z.-H. Wang, Y.-L. Jiang, and K.-L. Xu, "Time domain and frequency domain model order reduction for discrete time-delay systems," *International Journal of Systems Science*, vol. 51, no. 12, pp. 2134–2149, 2020.
- [8] R. A. de Andrade, P. R. Barros, and R. B. Lima, "Identification of Low Order Laguerre Plus Time-Delay Models with Optimal Pole Estimation," in *12th IFAC Symposium on Dynamics and Control of Process Systems including Biosystems (DYCOPS)*, vol. 52, no. 1, Florianopolis, Brazil, 2019, pp. 424–429.
- [9] V. Bro and A. Medvedev, "Identification of Continuous Volterra Models with Explicit Time Delay through Series of Laguerre Functions," in *2019 IEEE 58th Conference on Decision and Control (CDC)*, 2019.
- [10] M. Sadeghi and M. Farrokhi, "Real-time identification of nonlinear multiple-input-multiple-output systems with unknown input time delay using Wiener model with Neuro-Laguerre structure," *International Journal of Adaptive Control and Signal Processing*, vol. 33, no. 1, pp. 157–174, 2018.
- [11] M. Alci and M. H. Asyali, "Nonlinear system identification via Laguerre network based fuzzy systems," *Fuzzy Sets and Systems*, vol. 160, no. 24, pp. 3518–3529, 2009.
- [12] A. Back and A.-C. Tsoi, "Nonlinear system identification using discrete Laguerre functions," *Journal of Systems Engineering*, vol. 6, no. 3, pp. 194–207, 1996.
- [13] M. Tabatabaei, "PID controller design based on Laguerre orthonormal functions," *Journal of Control Engineering and Applied Informatics*, vol. 18, no. 4, pp. 65–76, 2016.
- [14] V. Karsky and M. Tuma, "Design PID controllers using generalized Laguerre functions," *Radioengineering*, vol. 31, no. 3, pp. 390–397, 2022.
- [15] C. Zervos and G. A. Dumont, "Deterministic adaptive control based on Laguerre series representation," *International Journal of Control*, vol. 48, no. 6, pp. 2333–2359, 1988.
- [16] G. Dumont, Y. Fu, and A.-L. Elshafei, "Orthonormal Functions in Identification and Adaptive Control," in *Intelligent Tuning and Adaptive Control*. Elsevier, 1991, pp. 193–198.
- [17] A. J. Rashidi, B. Karimi, and A. Khodaparast, "A Constrained Predictive Controller for AUV and Computational Optimization Using Laguerre Functions in Unknown Environments," *International Journal of Control, Automation and Systems*, vol. 18, no. 3, pp. 753–767, 2019.
- [18] G. Zhang, L. Gao, H. Yang, and L. Mei, "A novel method of model predictive control on permanent magnet synchronous machine with Laguerre functions," *Alexandria Engineering Journal*, vol. 60, no. 6, pp. 5485–5494, 2021.
- [19] M. Liu, H. Wu, J. Wang, and C. Wang, "Non-minimal state space model predictive control using Laguerre functions for reference tracking," *Asian Journal of Control*, vol. 24, no. 1, pp. 205–216, 2022.
- [20] M. H. Etefagh, J. D. Dona, F. Towhidkhal, and M. Naraghi, "Adaptive-pole selection in the Laguerre parametrisation of model predictive control to achieve high performance," *International Journal of Systems Science*, vol. 52, no. 16, pp. 3539–3555, 2021.
- [21] P. Olivier, "Online system identification using Laguerre series," *IEE Proceedings - Control Theory and Applications*, vol. 141, no. 4, pp. 249–254, 1994.
- [22] J. Kasac, T. Zilic, V. Milic, and A. Jokic, "Frequency-shifting-based stable on-line algebraic parameter identification of linear systems," *Journal of the Franklin Institute*, vol. 355, no. 18, pp. 9224–9244, 2018.
- [23] J. Kasac, D. Majetic, and D. Brezak, "An algebraic approach to on-line signal denoising and derivatives estimation," *Journal of the Franklin Institute*, vol. 355, no. 15, pp. 7799–7825, 2018.
- [24] P. Olivier, "Approximate system inverses," *Electronics Letters*, vol. 31, no. 23, pp. 2050–2051, 1995.
- [25] J. Kasac, A. Pender, M. Pranjic, and D. Kotarski, "Frequency-shifting-based algebraic approach to extended state observer design," *Asian Journal of Control*, vol. 23, no. 5, pp. 2171–2184, 2021.